

EMERGING THERAPIES AND MANAGEMENT STRATEGIES FOR FIBRODYSPLASIA OSSIFICANS PROGRESSIVA

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ABSTRACT

Fibrodysplasia ossificans progressiva (FOP) is an extremely rare and severely disabling autosomal dominant genetic disorder. It is primarily characterized by episodic, painful flare-ups involving soft tissue swelling, leading to the progressive formation of bone in areas where it does not normally occur. These episodes result in heterotopic ossification, where skeletal muscle and connective tissues, such as tendons, ligaments, and fascia, are progressively replaced by bone. Over time, this process severely restricts mobility and function, leading to profound disability.

FOP is caused by mutations in the **ACVR1 gene**, which plays a crucial role in bone growth and development. The pathological ossification typically begins in early childhood and progressively worsens, affecting not only movement but also respiratory function due to ossification in the rib cage.

Despite its rarity, FOP poses significant challenges for treatment, as there is currently no cure, and interventions like surgical removal of excess bone often exacerbate the condition. Current management strategies focus on symptom relief, pain management, and minimizing trauma that can trigger ossification.

However, recent advancements in molecular biology and genetic research have opened new avenues for therapeutic development. Promising emerging therapies, such as **gene-targeted treatments, inhibition of bone morphogenetic pathways, and immune-modulating therapies**, (M.Viswakanth 2018) offer hope for more effective management of the disease in the future. This review aims to explore these emerging therapies and management strategies, highlighting their potential to improve the quality of life for individuals affected by FOP.

INTRODUCTION

Fibrodysplasia Ossificans Progressiva (FOP) is an exceptionally rare genetic disorder characterized by the progressive transformation of soft tissues, such as muscles, ligaments, and tendons, into bone, a process known as heterotopic ossification. This pathological metamorphosis results in the gradual restriction of movement and the formation of an extra-skeletal framework, leading to significant physical limitations for affected individuals. The condition often manifests early in childhood, with ossification typically beginning in the neck and shoulder regions and progressing downward through the body, including the limbs. A hallmark of FOP is the congenital malformation of the big toes, medically referred to as *hallux valgus*, which is often one of the earliest diagnostic indicators.

The process of heterotopic ossification in FOP is episodic, marked by flare-ups of pre-osseous soft tissue swellings, which often begin in early childhood and continue to progress throughout the individual's life. These flare-ups frequently occur spontaneously but may also be triggered by trauma, surgical interventions, or viral infections. Over time, the ossification extends to major joints such as the neck, shoulders, elbows, hips, knees, wrists, and ankles, resulting in stiffness, limited movement, and eventual fusion (ankylosis) of the affected areas.

In addition to abnormal toe development, FOP is associated with various skeletal malformations, including deformities of the cervical spine and ribs. These abnormalities, along with the formation of bone in soft tissues, contribute to the overall rigidity and physical challenges faced by those with the disorder. The

severity of FOP varies among individuals, but most patients experience a steady decline in mobility as the condition advances. The underlying cause of FOP has been traced to a mutation in the ACVR1 gene, which encodes for a protein in the bone morphogenetic protein (BMP) pathway. This pathway plays a critical role in the formation of bones during embryonic development and in the repair of skeletal tissue postnatally.

AETIOLOGY

A large body of work has supported dysregulated bone morphogenetic protein (BMP) signaling in the pathogenesis of FOP. A single common heterozygous mutation (617G>A; R206H) has been identified in the cytoplasmic domain of activin receptor IA/activin-like kinase 2 (ACVR1/ALK2), a BMP type I receptor, in affected individuals of five small multigenerational families and in all sporadically affected individuals with the features of classic FOP [14]. All atypical FOP patients have heterozygous ACVR1 missense mutations in conserved amino acids [11]. Novel ACVR1 mutations have been described for FOP variants and in two cases of FOP plus [11]. To date, all ACVR1 mutations evaluated for enhanced BMP signaling are gain-of-function mutations [11,15]. Mounting evidence suggests that involvement of the inflammatory component of the immune system plays a critical role in FOP [16]. The presence of macrophages, lymphocytes and mast cells in early FOP lesions, macrophage and lymphocyte-associated death of skeletal Figure 5 Three-dimensional reconstructed computed tomography (CT) scan of the back of a twelve-year old child showing extensive heterotopic ossification typical of FOP. Reprinted from reference 14. Authors retain copyright. Pignolo et al. Orphanet Journal of Rare Diseases 2011, 6:80 <http://www.ajrd.com/content/6/1/80> Page 3 of 6 muscle, flare-ups following viral infections, the intermittent timing of flare-ups, and the beneficial response of early flare-ups to corticosteroids support involvement of the innate immune system in the pathogenesis of FOP [17]. Diagnosis and diagnostic methods Clinical suspicion of FOP early in life on the basis of malformed great toes can lead to early clinical diagnosis and the avoidance of harmful diagnostic and treatment procedures. Routine biochemical evaluations do not contribute to making the diagnosis. Plain x-rays can substantiate more subtle great toe abnormalities and the presence of HO (Robert J Pignolo 2011) Abnormal findings on bone scan occur before HO can be detected by conventional radiography, but sophisticated imaging studies are generally superfluous from a diagnostic standpoint. Confirmatory genetic testing is available on a clinical and research basis at several laboratories [18].

MOLECULAR MECHANISMS OF PATHOGENESIS IN FOP

The extracellular domain of ALK2 (a type I receptor) binds to several ligands in the TGF- β family, such as BMP-6, BMP-7, BMP9, and activin B, in co-operation with type II receptors, such as BMP receptor type II (BMPRII), activin receptor type IIA (ActRIIA), and activin receptor type IIB (ActRIIB) (Fig. 2). Because type II receptors are constitutively active Ser/Thr kinases, ALK2 is phosphorylated in a ternary complex formed in response to ligand binding at the cell membrane (Fig. 2). The GS domain, which is a stretch consisting of glycine and serine residues, has been identified as the site of phosphorylation by type II receptors [16]. Phosphorylated ALK2 activates kinase activity and phosphorylates Ser and Thr residues in downstream substrates, such as Smad1, Smad5, and Smad8/9 [17-19]. Phosphorylated Smad proteins regulate the transcription of target genes in the nucleus [20,21]. Transient over-expression of the mutant ALK2 associated with FOP, but not of wild-type ALK2, activates intracellular signaling without adding exogenous ligands, suggesting that these are gain-of-function mutations [22-25]. The mutant ALK2 associated with FOP is hypersensitive to the kinase activity of the type II receptors [25]. The 12 kDa FK506-binding protein (FKBP12) acts as a repressor of the kinase activity of type I receptors in the TGF- β family, including ALK2, by binding to their unphosphorylated intracellular domains [26]. It has been proposed that mutations in the intracellular domains of ALK2 associated with FOP reduce binding affinity to FKBP12 and activate downstream intracellular signaling in patients.

CONCLUSION

In recent years, significant progresses have been made in understanding the molecular mechanism underlying FOP and developing FOP therapies. The discovery of causative mutations in ALK2 has made it a promising druggable target for FOP. Numerous small-molecular inhibitors and antibodies targeting ALK2 have been developed. Among them, Saracatinib, DS-6016a, and BLU-782 are currently in FOP clinical trials. In addition, as activin A abnormally transduces BMP signaling in FOP, REGN2477 antibody-targeting activin A has been studied for the treatment of FOP, and its efficacy is currently under evaluation in a Phase II clinical trial. Moreover, potential drugs targeting transcriptional effectors associated with the early heterotopic ossification have also shown promise in the treatment of FOP, and their efficacies are being evaluated in clinical trials. For instance, a Phase II clinical trial has showed that RAR γ agonist Palovarotene effectively reduces the percentage of FOP patients developing heterotopic ossification and the time to remission (NCT02190747) [74]. Homozygous dominant form is more severe than the heterozygous form. Person having FOP should any injuries to muscle tissues, traumatic injuries, and fractures they may aggravate the ossification. The ACVR1 gene provides instructions for making the activin receptor type 1 protein, which is a member of a protein family called bone morphogenetic protein (BMP) type 1 receptors. Activin receptor type 1 is normally activated at appropriate times by molecules called ligands, like BMPs. FKBP12 inhibits activin receptor.

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